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History of urban malaria control in Africa: case studies of three contemporary cities

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Abstract

Background: Some of the world's most populous cities lie in the malaria endemic regions of Africa and ongoing urbanisation exposes increasingly large numbers of people to the risk of urban malaria. This is not a new problem and understanding the efforts to control urban malaria in the past can help inform the design of effective malaria control and prevention programmes now and for the future.

Methods: Lagos (Nigeria), Dar es Salaam (Tanzania) and Kinshasa (Democratic Republic of the Congo) were selected for analysis. Historical urban area limits were researched, geo-rectified and digitized. Population estimates and historical data of malaria incidence, infection prevalence and malaria control efforts were assembled and digitally mapped. Data used in the analysis included only those that were located within the urban extents at the time that the survey was undertaken.

Surveys were standardized to the 2 to 10 year age group ($PfPR_{2-10}$) using catalytic conversion models.

Results: All three cities were established in areas with intense malaria transmission. Between 1900 and 1959, the reported mean $PfPR_{2-10}$ was 57% in Lagos, 50% in Dar es Salaam and 69% in Kinshasa.

By 2012, mean $PfPR_{2-10}$ had declined to 7% in Lagos, 21% in Kinshasa and 12% in Dar es Salaam.

Malaria control and prevention activities included environmental modification, house screening, larviciding, antimalarial prophylaxis and treatment, widespread use of insecticides in the 1940s and 1950s, indoor residual spraying and more recently the distribution of insecticide-impregnated bed-nets and active case detection, diagnosis and treatment.

Conclusions: Despite various waves of effort for malaria control and prevention in these three cities, many millions of people remain at risk. The urban environment presents specific problems of heterogeneity in malaria risk and transmission that require bespoke and responsive interventions.

Introduction

By 2030, 60% of the world's population is expected to live in cities. The population of urban areas grew by an astonishing 1 billion people between 2000 and 2014. The United Nations estimates that more than 90% of future urban population growth will be in low- and middle-income countries (LMICs) [1]. In 1900 less than 2% of Africans lived in cities, in 2018 an estimated 43% of the population were urban and this is projected to grow to 48% by 2030 and 59% by 2050 [2].

Comparatively well-resourced versus rural communities, cities have more health workers, financial resources and facilities, better electricity supply, refrigeration, and supply chain management. High population density facilitates large-scale access to healthcare facilities and services. However, cities deserve special attention for the control of communicable diseases because they are also vulnerable. High levels of population mobility, both local and international, increases the risk of disease transmission, and high population densities can cause people to be clustered around risks. Rapid urbanization can introduce diseases mostly prevalent in remote rural areas into cities.

As cities grow, so do the inequities within them. Whole sub-populations may be considerably worse off than their urban neighbours, and sometimes their rural counterparts. Inequities affecting such large populations cause immense humanitarian suffering and compromise the ability to meet global development targets. In-migrants to urban areas often live under the radar, with poor access to healthcare. They may be unaware of the health risks in their environment and how to avoid them, and dissociated from municipal services and public health interventions.

Urban malaria risk is characterised by marked heterogeneity in transmission and infection risk over small areas [3]. A systematic review of urban malaria in sub-Saharan Africa identified man-made,

urban vector breeding sites, including urban agriculture, tyre tracks, and ditches, as common breeding sites for malaria vectors and low socioeconomic status as a significant risk factor for malaria [4]. Overall, however, urban growth has been associated reduced malaria risk [5], with evidence that vectors are less numerous per person and the malaria prevalence lower in cities than in adjacent rural areas [6, 7]. Nevertheless, given the vast numbers of people living in cities and high population densities, even a low risk of malaria can translate into a considerable public health problem [3, 8]. It should also be recognised that urban centres are the drivers of economic growth. Thus, the detrimental socio-economic impact of malaria in urban areas will be larger proportionally compared with rural areas.

In the face of massive urban expansion, and growing inequities within cities, it is important to recognise the specific challenges and opportunities for malaria control and elimination in the urban environment. Given the large populations living in urban areas in malaria endemic countries, meeting current targets established by the World Health Organization (WHO) for reductions in malaria mortality, morbidity and elimination will require that urban malaria is adequately addressed [9].

It is important that we should not forget the lessons of the past. In this paper we consider the historical approaches for malaria control and prevention in urban areas in Africa, with particular attention to three rapidly growing megacities, Lagos, Dar es Salaam and Kinshasa. The aim is to examine how these historical insights might inform current approaches to decrease malaria transmission and the burden of disease in urban populations.

Historical approaches to urban malaria across Africa

Despite significant geographical and political diversity, the history of urban malaria control in Africa follows a broadly common thread. Urban malaria control in Africa had its beginnings in the protection of European colonists, many of whom were concentrated in towns that were growing rapidly as trade increased. European death rates were still high in Africa at the end of the 19th century, with tropical diseases seen as a barrier to mass colonisation [10, 11]. Port cities were vulnerable to malaria epidemics as they grew rapidly and included many new colonists and military personnel with no natural immunity. The population of non-official Europeans, mainly miners and labourers also increased, usually housed in poor conditions in tents and shacks [10]. Mosquito nets were used by Europeans to exclude mosquitos to prevent biting while asleep, but were fragile and often improperly deployed, providing poor protection [11]. Improvements in housing, particularly for soldiers moved from tents to barracks, did reduce exposure to mosquitos [11]. House screening on windows and balconies of colonial buildings with metal gauze also effectively excluded mosquitoes [12]. Thus, as European colonies became more established and housing improved, death rates tended to fall even in the absence of medical advances [11].

With the acceptance in the early 20th century of the role of mosquitoes in transmitting malaria, vector control interventions were implemented in many colonial cities for 'tropical sanitation'. In British colonies, 'Mosquito Brigades' were adopted with the aim of identifying and eliminating mosquito breeding sites, though with varying levels of vigour, resources, authority and success. Interventions included environmental modifications, such as filling ditches, draining swamps, and clearing water courses to increase flow, as well as stocking wells with fish and larviciding with fuel oil [12]. Malaria control efforts were later expanded to protect African populations, generally by missionary organisations or colonial employers. Large environmental engineering projects with the twin aims of reclaiming land for growing cities and reducing mosquito breeding sites were also

undertaken. However, greater mobility of the population, particularly after the establishment of railways, increased immigration and urbanisation, promoted rural-to-urban transmission and thwarted control efforts. During colonial wars and later in World War I, population displacement and troop movements also promoted malaria outbreaks [13-16].

The prophylactic use of quinine was common in British colonies throughout the tropics from the mid-19th century, and it is thought to have reduced malaria mortality in African colonies [11, 17]. In French colonies, even by the time of World War I, quinine was not regularly used as a prophylactic, and high death rates persisted in malaria-naïve soldiers and colonists into the twentieth century [11]. This contrasts with the approach in German colonies. Robert Koch had discovered that malaria immunity was not based on race, as was previously believed, but gained gradually over time and that children under five years of age most often died from malaria. It was his former assistant, Heinrich Ollwig who conducted an expedition against malaria in Dar es Salaam in 1901–1904 (*Malariabekämpfungsexpedition*) which included mass distribution of quinine prophylaxis to all infected persons and for individual prophylaxis of the non-immune populations [18-20]. Quinine prophylaxis was also recommended in the north of Deutsch-Südwestafrika (German Southwest Africa) [20].

A further consequence of Koch's findings that children were susceptible to malaria was that children were assumed to be the parasite's natural host. British scientists Christophers and Stephens confirmed Koch's findings and supported the (incorrect) conclusion that malaria prevention required Europeans to be separated from African children [21]. Thus, the leading malaria scientists of the time recommended physical separation of European and African populations with buffer zones between the populations. Segregation became an official policy of the British Empire in 1900, and was implemented throughout the colonies [10]. However, though segregation efforts were adopted

by colonial governments, and strictly enforced among officials and the military, their more general application became increasingly onerous and impractical in the busy port cities of Africa.

World War II again saw the need to protect European and Colonial armies from malaria while fighting across Africa and visiting her ports. Mass migration and greater mobility afforded by the expansion of roads and access to motor transport facilitated the spread of disease [22]. This era saw the first implementation of the insecticide dichlorodiphenyltrichloroethane (DDT) in Africa as well as the introduction of chloroquine prophylaxis. Notably, vector control measures, including mass spraying of DDT and environmental management enthusiastically promoted by Dr Fred Soper in Egypt resulted in malaria elimination in that country in the 1940s [23, 24]. The widespread use of DDT and chloroquine also dramatically reduced malaria mortality in South Asia and the Middle East, but similar interventions had little impact on malaria mortality in tropical Africa [25].

Post war, the political initiative for malaria control and prevention shifted from the old colonial powers, as they rebuilt and recovered, to the United States. This occurred via NGOs like the Rockefeller Foundation, as well as various US Government agencies until these were merged into US Agency for International Development (USAID) in 1961. Improving the health of African populations was a key component in securing political aims, while achieving economic improvements and increased productivity [26-29]. Malaria, in particular, became the classic 'economic disease', seen as a major barrier to development, and the solution was to prevent transmission and treat cases [27, 29, 30]. The new weapons of DDT and chloroquine were to achieve these aims where previous malaria control and prevention efforts had failed [29]. Consequently, malaria eradication emerged as a rational economic proposition to provide the best return on investment and in 1955 the newly formed WHO launched the Global Malaria Eradication Program (GMEP) [13].

In the 1960s, malaria eradication programmes under GMEP were launched or piloted across most of Africa and in Asia, the Americas and Europe. The programme spanned the period of Africa gaining independence from European colonial powers and incorporated the first continent-wide programme aimed at controlling malaria in African populations. Scaling up of resources and personnel was challenging, whereas confidence in science and technology was high. Consequently, the GMEP programme was over reliant on DDT for mass spraying of vector habitats and indoor residual spraying (IRS) as well as chloroquine for both prophylaxis and treatment. Action occurred in advance of the necessary research to support implementation and these issues were recognised at the time; in 1961 the key research areas that needed to be addressed included a lack of local epidemiology data, limited surveillance, poor understanding of vector behaviour and vector resistance to insecticides, insufficient methods for the assessment of insecticide efficacy, the need to develop new antimalarial drugs and to develop improved knowledge of optimal antimalarial administration [31]. As had been experienced with the mosquito brigades of colonial times, there was resistance from populations to interventions that interfered with their daily lives or invaded their homes. Migration was also identified as a key factor undermining malaria eradication [31]. All of these challenges persist and are familiar to the malaria researchers of today.

GMEP did not achieve malaria elimination in any country in Africa, though was successful elsewhere, including Europe and the Americas [32, 33]. As early as 1963, the United States had ended its contributions to the WHO special malaria eradication account [27]. By 1969, WHO discontinued GMEP and investment in malaria control and prevention generally decreased in Africa, particularly during the economic crisis of the 1970s. Throughout Africa only Morocco has been certified malaria-free since 1955, with malaria elimination potentially achievable by 2020 in Algeria, Botswana, Cabo Verde, Comoros, South Africa and Swaziland [33].

By the end of the 20th century, parasite resistance to chloroquine and vector resistance to DDT and related compounds caused a resurgence in malaria across Africa and a steep increase in mortality which persisted into the first decade of the 21st century, stimulating a global response [34]. For example, the Multilateral Initiative on Malaria (MIM) was established in 1997 with a mission to strengthen and sustain collaborative malaria research and training in Africa; the Roll Back Malaria (RBM) Partnership was formed in 1998 by the WHO, the United Nations Children's Fund (UNICEF), the United Nations Development Program (UNDP) and the World Bank as a global platform for coordinated action targeting malaria, including African malaria-endemic countries; in 2002, the Global Fund to fight AIDS, tuberculosis and malaria was established as partnership between governments, civil society, the private sector and people affected by the diseases to raise and distribute money for locally driven programmes targeting these diseases; the United Kingdom Department for International Development (DFID) identified malaria as a priority for investment; and more recently, in 2005 the President's Malaria Initiative (PMI) was launched aiming to reduce the burden of malaria and help relieve poverty on the African continent. In concert with these initiatives, there was renewed vigour in malaria research and development, long neglected. This included the establishment of portfolio research organisations for antimalarial drugs (Medicines for Malaria Venture), vaccines (Malaria Vaccine Initiative) and insecticides/larvicides (Innovative Vector Control Consortium), as well as the development of rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs) for malaria and substantial investments from industry in research and development infrastructure and capacity building. Funding of malaria control and treatment also benefitted from increased finance from endemic countries.

Since the millennium, mass distribution of insecticide-treated nets (ITNs), long-lasting insecticide-treated bed nets (LLINs), IRS and the development and deployment of RDTs and artemisinin-based combination therapies (ACTs) have reduced malaria mortality and prevalence in many settings,

including in urban areas [34, 35]. However, despite new tools and increased access to interventions, malaria remains endemic across most of Africa with large urban populations at risk of the disease.

Urban malaria case studies

Methods

Three rapidly growing colonial cities, Lagos (Nigeria), Dar es Salaam (Tanzania) and Kinshasa (Democratic Republic of the Congo) were selected for analysis, based on the richness of empirical data available and their high contemporary malaria burdens. The historical urban area limits for the three study cities were assembled from historical maps obtained from various sources [18, 36-40]. Maps were geo-rectified to World Geodetic System 1984 datum and digitized onscreen in ArcGIS version 10 (ESRI, Redlands, USA). The total surface area of the extents in each mapped year was then calculated using geometry tool in ArcGIS 10 and validated using supplementary information on area estimates where available. Population estimates in for 1950–2012 were obtained from the 2011 World urbanization prospects database [41]. Pre-1950 population estimates were collated from various sources [36, 42, 43]. For each city, historical data of malaria incidence, infection prevalence and malaria control efforts were assembled from a variety of archives in Nigeria, Tanzania and DRC. Detailed searches of colonial administration annual medical reports, that included laboratory, clinical and survey data, (1900–1959/60) were obtained from the British Library/National Archives in London; the Wellcome Library (now Ministry of Health Library) at the National Public Health Laboratories in Nairobi, Kenya; the archives of the Tropical Medicine Institute at Antwerp; and the WHO archives in Geneva and Brazzaville. Further, national survey data reports in Tanzania in the 1960s were obtained from manual searches at the National Institute for Medical Research (NMIR) library located at Amani. Data on malaria parasite prevalence in the three cities was assembled as part of the larger Information for Malaria (INFORM) project [44].

Online electronic databases were used to identify peer-reviewed, published data on malaria infection prevalence published between [X] and [2012?], as previously described [44]. Titles and abstracts from all publication searches were used to identify possible cross-sectional survey data undertaken in a variety of forms: either as community surveys, school surveys, intervention trials (where pre-intervention, baseline and control groups could be identified). For each survey identified, information was assembled on the description of the study area (name, administrative divisions and geographical coordinates, if available), the dates of start and end of the survey (month and year) and information about blood examination (number of individuals tested, number positive for *Plasmodium* infections by species), the methods used to detect infection (microscopy, rapid diagnostic tests (RDTs), polymerase chain reaction or combinations) and the lowest and highest age in the surveyed population. Where a community was surveyed repeatedly in time only the first survey was included unless subsequent surveys were separated by at least five months from the initial survey to control for the effect of interventions given in the preceding survey.

The geographic coordinates of each survey location were established by global positioning systems, digital resources including Microsoft Encarta Encyclopaedia (Microsoft, 2004) and Google Earth and others. Survey points along the coastline were verified to be within land as defined by administrative boundaries from the 2008 Global administrative unit layer (GAUL) database [45]. Survey points were also checked against the Global Lakes and Wetlands (GLWD) database to ensure inland points were also within defined land area [46]. Survey points whose geographic coordinates were not found were excluded from the dataset.

Data used in the analysis included only those that were located within the urban extents of the time that the survey was undertaken. In addition, only surveys with a minimum sample size of 15 were included to control for precision bias in malaria prevalence due low sample sizes [47]. Because

surveys used different age groups, data were standardised to the 2 to 10 year age group ($PfPR_{2-10}$) using catalytic conversion models [48].

Lagos, Nigeria

Population and geography

Lagos is a port city on the Atlantic coast and the most populous city in Nigeria and in Africa. It progressively became an important commercial centre on the West African coast and was declared a British colony in 1862. In 1914, Lagos became the capital of the Colony and Protectorate of Nigeria. During the colonial era, Lagos Island was divided along the MacGregor canal that separated the densely populated African town and the European residential area at Ikoyi. The Lagos metropolitan area now occupies Lagos Island, Ikoyi Island, Victoria Island and has extended to a large area on the mainland. From an area of less than 50 km² on Lagos Island in 1911, Lagos has extended more than 40 km north-west of Lagos Island covering an area of close to 1000 km² by 2013 (Figure 1) [36, 38, 40]. The population of Lagos metropolis has grown rapidly over the last 100 years. With an estimated population close to 14 million in 2016 [49], by 2030, it is estimated that Lagos will be the 9th largest city in the world with over 24 million population [50].

Figure 1. The change in spatial extent of Lagos between 1963 (69.9 km²) and 2013 (738 km²).

Total surface area of the extents was calculated using the geometry tool in ArcGIS 10 as described in the methods and validated using supplementary information [36, 38, 40].

Historical malaria trends in Lagos

Malaria has been reported as a major clinical problem in Lagos from the 1900s. Between 1897 and 1900 infant mortality was 403–453/1000 live births per annum in Lagos, mainly attributable to ‘fever’ [10]. By 1917, malaria represented 8.8% of the total cases treated at the government hospital in Lagos [51]. A decrease in reported cases was witnessed between 1929 and 1953; a period where population density increased rapidly (Figure 2) [51].

Figure 2. Annual malaria incidence and population growth, Lagos 1909–1953. Black bars represent malaria cases per 1,000 population for each year. The red line shows total population growth trend in the same period.

Malaria case data assembled from annual medical and sanitary reports for the colony of Nigeria published between 1915 and 1954. Case data converted to annual incidence, denominator derived from population estimates in 1909 and 1931 [51] and United Nations population data for 1950 and 1955. Inter-censal growth rates between census years computed to estimate populations for non-census years. No Lagos-specific malaria cases are given in the annual medical reports from 1918–1928, 1939–1943 and 1949–1951. Clinical diagnosis used for most reported malaria cases reported between 1909 and 1917. Slide confirmed malaria cases reported between 1929 and 1938.

The malaria parasite rates within Lagos Metropolis between 1900 and 2012 are shown in Figure 3. A total of 127 malaria parasite community surveys conducted in Lagos between 1900 and 2012 were

identified. Fifteen surveys that did not meet the inclusion criteria (less than 15 persons examined or conducted across areas that exceeded 25 km²) were excluded from the analysis. The mean *PfPR*₂₋₁₀ of four surveys within the Lagos urban extents of 1900–1959 was 57%. Malaria parasite rates remained high in Lagos between 1960 and 1979 with a mean *PfPR*₂₋₁₀ of 51% from 13 surveys conducted within the Lagos urban extents at that time. There was a gradual decrease in parasite rates across the Lagos metropolis between 1980 and 2012. A mean *PfPR*₂₋₁₀ of 24% was reported from four surveys conducted between 1980 and 2005. The mean *PfPR*₂₋₁₀ between 2006 and 2012 was 7%, with only seven out of 44 surveys conducted between 2006 and 2012 reporting a parasite rate of greater than 10%, mostly located in the peri-urban areas away from the city centre.

Figure 3. Age standardized *P. falciparum* malaria parasite rates (*PfPR*₂₋₁₀) in Lagos metropolis 1900–2012.

Box plot showing median (central lines), 25% and 75% quartile ranges around the median (box width) and upper and lower limits (T). Number of individuals examined by time period: 1900–1959 (13,212); 1960–1979 (7,754); 1980–2005 (6,622) and 2006–2012 (2,406).

Malaria control and prevention in Lagos

Organized anti-mosquito efforts in Lagos began as early as 1900 but were initially confined to domestic sanitation and prevention of breeding close to populated areas [52]. Vector control

measures were promoted in urban areas, focused primarily on protecting colonial administration employees. Quinine was taken as prophylaxis by the Europeans and local government employees and was issued free of charge in schools and prisons [52, 53]. Malaria control practices between 1900 and 1931 included weekly inspection of houses by 'mosquito brigades', responsible for identifying and destroying mosquito breeding sites [52], and swamp reclamation through dredging to increase water flow, draining or filling up marshes and making embankments [53]. Larval control measures, such as ditching, oiling, and stocking wells with fish were also adopted [53]. The European quarters were segregated from the indigenous quarters in many sections of Lagos using buffer zones that were stringently controlled to 'protect' the European residents from infection [52, 54]. African children, who were seen as the principle reservoir of infection, were relocated to adjacent native villages as late as 1940 [54].

During the World War II, swamp drainage was intensified and tidal flooding control introduced. The Lagos mosquito control scheme, established in 1942, initially focussed on the control of *An. melas* near the Royal Air Force airport at Apapa but was later extended to cover other parts of Lagos metropolis [54, 55]. By 1945, 1677 acres of swamp had been reclaimed [54]. In 1948, the Malaria Service was initiated under the Colonial Development and Welfare Act [55], establishing permanent larvicidal teams responsible for the control of *An. gambiae* s.l. using gasoline and/or DDT [55, 56]. Tidal swamps were reduced from 19.5 km² to 4 km² by 1951 through land reclamation [55, 56], plus maintenance and extension of existing schemes for drainage, reclamation and larviciding.

After independence in 1960, mosquito control programs continued in Lagos [57]. Spraying of houses and oiling of breeding areas was carried out on a limited scale. Land reclamation programmes accelerated in this period owing to the demands of the rapidly expanding population and industry. Reports from as early as 1959 suggest that anti-malarial drugs purchased from retailers were widely

available in the home, including mepacrine, quinine and paludrine [58]. By 1963, malaria prevalence had decreased in the city; attributed to the relative affluence of Lagos and the availability of anti-malarial drugs in clinics and other treatment centres [56, 57].

Population expansion from 1.2 million in the 1960s to 10 million by 1991 resulted in significant environmental changes in Lagos, eliminating most natural vector breeding sites [59]. However, rapid urbanisation created numerous man-made mosquito breeding sites. The diversity of these micro-environments was perhaps reflected in the presence of multiple vector species in the city (*An. gambiae*, *An. arabiensis*, *An. funestus*) with different biting times, and preferences for indoor/outdoor biting, complicating control and prevention [60]. A survey conducted in 2005 during the peak transmission season found 292 potential *Anopheles* breeding sites, of which about a quarter were positive for *Anopheles* larvae; all were *An. gambiae* complex [61]. Of concern was the level of pollution that the larvae were able to tolerate, suggesting that they were successfully adapting to the urban environment and expanding their potential breeding sites [61].

In recent years, The Lagos Malaria Control Strategy Plan 2009–2013 incorporated an integrated vector management programme, including larviciding, IRS, environmental management and distribution of ITN/LLINs within the Lagos state [62, 63]. However, implementation was hampered by inadequate entomological surveillance data and the programmatic effectiveness of the prevention strategies was sub-optimal [64]. Although over 1 million LLINs were distributed in Lagos state between 2006 and 2008, there were still significant gaps in LLIN use in urban areas [65]. In 2007 an estimated 60% of children in urban Lagos slept under nets [66], but data from 2016–2017 indicated that only 24% of children under 5 years of age slept under an LLIN the previous night [67]. There are no data regarding the effectiveness of IRS in urban Lagos, though studies in rural districts of Lagos indicate IRS reduces the odds of parasitemia in children under five [68].

Dar es Salaam, Tanzania

Population and geography

Dar es Salaam is located on a bay of the Indian Ocean on the east African coastline. Originally a small fishing village, it expanded into a harbour town in 1862 under the Sultan of Zanzibar. In 1887, the German East Africa Company overthrew the Arabic rulers and colonized the East African coast with Dar es Salaam becoming the administrative and commercial centre of German East Africa. By 1900, an estimated 20,000 people lived in the town. In 1913, the town was divided in two: the European quarter along the beach, with the 'natives' (African, Arabs and Asians) settled in houses further inland [69]. The population of Dar es Salaam grew rapidly as more immigrants seeking employment came into the city and settled in nearby peri-urban areas.

During World War I, intense fighting in the region, coupled with a serious drought in 1917–18, forced much of Dar es Salaam's African population to migrate upcountry. Combined with the decampment of thousands of Europeans, there was a decrease in the town's population from 34,000 in 1914 to 16,886 by 1921 [43]. After the war, now under British rule as the capital of Tanganyika, Dar es Salaam experienced an economic boom and growth accelerated. The 1940s and 1950s saw the emergence of several residential settlements such as Oyster Bay (European), Upanga (Indian), Kinondoni, Magomeni & Temeke (African). Dar es Salaam remained the capital of the newly independent United Republic of Tanzania from 1961 until 1973, when the capital was relocated to Dodoma. Dar es Salaam almost doubled its population from 2.5 million inhabitants in 2002 to 4.4 million in 2012 [70]. With an estimated population of 5.78 million in 2018 [71], Dar es Salaam is among the fastest growing cities in Africa (Figure 4) [18].

Figure 4. Change in spatial extent of Dar es Salaam between 1967 (71.4 km²) and 2013 (1167 km²).

Total surface area of the extents was calculated using the geometry tool in ArcGIS 10 as described in the methods and validated using supplementary information [18].

Historical malaria trends in Dar es Salaam

Dar es Salaam has a hot and humid tropical climate with two rainy seasons, with the intense rainy season falling between March and May. Malaria is endemic and perennial and predominantly caused by *P. falciparum*, though *P. malariae*, *P. ovale* and *P. vivax* have also been reported [18, 72, 73].

Malaria was a notifiable disease in Dar es Salaam from 1921 [74]. While malaria morbidity was fairly well documented among European and Asian communities living in Dar es Salaam, data among the African population was unreliable as the majority of clinical cases among this population were not seen by medical practitioners [74]. Between 1906 and 1912, an average of 4,700 cases was reported among a population of approximately 25,000, *circa* 188 cases per 1,000 population-at-risk annually. Thereafter, annual malaria case incidence reduced to 108 cases per 1,000 population-at-risk between 1921 and 1922 among a population of approximately 25,000. Malaria accounted for close to 70% of all out-patient illnesses treated in Dar es Salaam by 1923. Slide confirmed case incidence was approximately 222 per 1,000 population-at-risk annually over the period 1923–1925, incidence dropped between 1926 and 1927, where-after it began to rise again (Figure 5) [43, 74-76]. However, by 1932, malaria accounted for less than 30% of all cases treated in Dar es Salaam with case incidence at 118 per 1000 population reported in 1932 [74].

Few data are available on malaria incidence between 1938 and 1948. However, immediately after World War II, malaria case incidence in Dar es Salaam was reported at 30 cases per 1000 population-at-risk. No comprehensive records on malaria cases in Dar es Salaam were identified after 1950s. Presently, it is suggested that over a million malaria cases are reported by the health facilities every year in Dar es Salaam [72, 77], though malaria in Dar es Salaam is often over reported [78-80] and cases are often imported from rural areas [79].

Figure 5. Annual malaria incidence and population growth, Dar es Salaam 1906–1949. Black bars represent malaria cases per 1,000 population for each year. The red line shows total population growth trend in the same period.

Malaria case data assembled from [75] and Colonial medical and sanitary reports for Dar es Salaam and Tanganyika Territory. Case data converted to annual incidence, denominator derived from population estimates 1900–1940 [43, 74, 76] and United Nations population data for 1950. Inter-censal growth rates between census years computed to estimate populations for non-census years. No Dar es Salaam-specific records of malaria cases found 1913–1921 and 1939–1948. Malaria case prevalence was recorded before 1923 and slide confirmed cases thereafter.

A mean $PfPR_{2-10}$ of 50% was observed in nine surveys conducted between 1900 and 1959 within Dar es Salaam, with the majority of the surveys reporting a parasite prevalence above 40% (Figure 6).

There was an apparent decline in malaria risk observed between 1960 and 1979, with a mean

parasite rate of 17%; only three of the 13 surveys conducted in this period reported a $PfPR_{2-10}$ above 20%. Between 2006 and 2012, the majority (88%) of the surveys reported a parasite rate below 20%.

Figure 6. Age standardized *P. falciparum* malaria parasite rates ($PfPR_{2-10}$) in Dar es Salaam 1900–2012.

Box plot showing median (central lines), 25% and 75% quartile ranges around the median (box width) and upper and lower limits (T). Number of individuals examined by time period: 1900–1959 (4,284); 1960–1979 (1,528); 1980–2005 (9,661) and 2006–2012 (20,818).

Malaria control, prevention in Dar es Salaam

Under German rule, anti-malaria efforts started in the 1890s, targeting mosquito control.

Environmental works, including oiling, swamp drainage and general sanitation improvement were introduced by 1901, principally in the European areas and undertaken by staff of the General Sanitary Authority using guidelines of the *Gesundheits* Commission [18, 42, 81, 82]. The German colonial press reported that coconut trees were planted to drain the soil [20]. However, permanent swamps encompassing the city and geological conditions that maintained numerous breeding sites even in the dry season rendered vector control efforts ineffective and these were considered too costly and soon abandoned [83, 84]. The focus of anti-malarial campaigns in Dar es Salaam switched

to malaria parasite control through mass administration of quinine beginning in 1901. All infected cases found through blood examination of all natives (African, Indians and Arabs) employed or living within European quarters and adjacent areas were treated with 1 gram of quinine on the 9th and 10th of the month for two months [75, 85].

The number of malaria cases per population reported in Dar es Salaam decreased from 74% in 1902 to 35% in 1904 representing a 50% reduction [84]. The blood sterilization campaign was taken over by the German military in 1904 who ran it until World War I [18, 83-85]. Limited staff numbers and the mobility of Dar es Salaam's growing population made it increasingly difficult to carry out general quinine administration and many inhabitants and visitors escaped treatment [74, 86]. Consequently, quinine administration was replaced as a primary malaria control measure with vector control [18, 75, 85, 86]. A German ordinance for mosquito extermination that provided legal sanctions for the destruction of ponds, vessels, tins, and other sources of standing water was put in place in 1913 [74].

Racial segregation for disease control was instituted in 1914 during the German occupation, with the city divided into three zones for Europeans, Asians and Africans. A buffer zone (sanitary zone) of 256 m was set between the European Quarters, and the Asian and African districts and later also between the Asian and African neighbourhoods. After World War I, the British continued the sanitary zone system, but it quickly became apparent that it was impossible to maintain because of the commercial and business activities of the city. The British Royal Army Medical Corps employed a brigade of 'mosquito boys' to inspect the town and identify and destroy mosquito breeding sites through oiling, and draining or filling holes and depressions [74, 76, 86]. Larvicides, like Paris green and larvivorous fish were also used [76, 81]. Additionally, government houses were mosquito-proofed and mosquito nets provided to all European and Asian officials [76]. In the 1930s, significant grants were made by the Colonial Development Fund to the engineering and environmental control

of malaria in Dar es Salaam; £34,330 between 1932 and 1936 (£1.74 million based on value in 2017) [73, 85]. In 1932, the installation of permanent drainage and filling works began at Gerezani creek, completed in 1937 [73, 76, 85]. Also in 1937, an ordinance for mosquito extermination including penalties to decrease household mosquito breeding was enacted [76]. Protective zones of strict malaria control were established between native and European settlements with routine surveys of anopheline breeding sites [42, 74]. In the 1940s, the role of sanitary ‘policemen’ included rural communities and emphasised education rather than punitive strategies [42]. Following World War II, DDT and Dieldrin were introduced for aerial spraying and IRS, as was prophylactic chloroquine [18, 42, 76, 82]. Routine anti-larval measures also continued between 1950 and 1960 [76].

After the country’s independence in 1961, malaria control activities under the Tanganyika Malaria Service (TMS) declined, limited to occasional spraying, larval source reduction and disease surveillance [85]. Residual spraying with Dieldrin was replaced with DDT in 1964 [85]. Adverse economic conditions and decentralization in the 1970s caused deterioration of the health system in many urban settings and malaria control efforts were neglected. Through the 1970s, activity in mosquito control measures reduced and chemotherapy was the only anti-malaria intervention in place [18]. Despite this relative lack of investment, there was no apparent resurgence in malaria until the 1980s.

In 1988, the Ministry of Health in Tanzania launched the urban malaria control programme (UMCP) funded by the Japanese International Cooperation Agency (JICA) [18]. The project ran until 1996, covering Dar es Salaam and Tanga cities and received equipment, technical and operational expertise from JICA amounting to US\$17 million, plus an additional US\$2.7 million from the Ministry of Health Tanzania, Dar es Salaam city council and Tanga municipal council. The project was primarily focused on vector control implemented weekly through larviciding and environmental

management around spatially stratified areas and peri-urban areas where IRS and ITNs were introduced. IRS was repeated every 3–6 months but suspended in 1993 and 1994 owing to lack of insecticides. A major contribution of the UMCP was the stereoscopic aerial photo interpretation routine that allowed the rapid identification of potential breeding sites and the elaboration of malaria risk map across the city [18]. Notably, community participation was more difficult to achieve than was anticipated [18]. The effect of the UMCP on larval and adult densities was evaluated through regular breeding site searches, room catches as well as using light traps. The study noted significant variations in mosquito catches which were affected by factors such as location and type of house, season and the use of insecticides [18]. Malaria prevalence was assessed among randomly selected school children 6–16 years old who were screened for malaria and treated with chloroquine. In these children, there was a significant decrease in parasite prevalence between 1988 and 1989 irrespective of the type of intervention. Parasite prevalence was higher in peri-urban versus urban areas and part of the observed decreases might have resulted from increasing urbanisation [18].

In 2004, UMCP was re-launched by the Dar es Salaam City Council as part of routine municipal services [87, 88]. Largely community-based, the UMCP included routine mapping and weekly surveillance of mosquito breeding habitats, like water puddles, swamps, drains, streams, construction pits, rice paddies and water storage containers. Weekly larviciding using *Bacillus sphaericus* (Bs,) and *Bacillus thuringiensis israelensis* (Bti), started in 2006, covering 15 wards in the three municipalities of Dar es Salaam. These activities were conducted by community-based resource persons (CORPs), recruited from within local communities via the elected local government [89], with an estimated annual cost of US\$559,476 [90]. Early evaluations indicated that after one year of community-based larviciding transmission by *An. gambiae* s.l., was reduced by 31% (95%CI 21.6, 37.6%; p=0.04) [87]. A cost-effectiveness analysis showed the programme to be very cost effective where malaria incidence is above 110–116 infections per 1,000 persons per year (above 40

infections per 1,000 was cost effective) [91]. Contemporary to the larviciding programme, there was scale-up of window screening via commercial distribution systems without any public subsidies or promotion [92]. A recent analysis indicated that the downward trend in malaria prevalence between 2004 and 2008, which was not previously reported or attributed to any explanatory factor, could be explained by the city-wide increase in window screening coverage (OR 0.07; 95%CI 0.05, 0.09; $p < 0.0001$) and progressive rollout of larviciding (OR 0.50; 95%CI 0.41, 0.60; $p < 0.0001$) [92]. This highlights the complexity in evaluating interventions in urban areas where multiple confounding factors can influence parasite prevalence. More recently, the National Malaria Medium Term Strategic Plan for Tanzania 2008 – 2013 aimed to cover 15 urban councils and scale up larviciding in five city councils, including Dar es Salaam.

Kinshasa, DRC

Population and geography

Kinshasa is the capital and the largest city of the Democratic Republic of the Congo (DRC). Formerly known as Léopoldville (French) or Leopoldstad (Dutch), Kinshasa is located along the south bank of the Congo River and developed from a Belgian trading post established by Henry Morton Stanley while in the employ of King Leopold of Belgium in 1881. In 1883, a second trading post was established upstream at Kinshasa village. Léopoldville–Kinshasa was consolidated in 1922 and became the colonial capital of the Belgian Congo from 1923. On independence in 1966, the city was renamed Kinshasa as the capital of the Democratic Republic of the Congo.

Under colonial rule, the city was predominantly occupied by the European population, and access by Africans was strictly controlled. Between 1930 and 1940, the city spread southwards with settlements around Ngiri-Ngiri. At the end of World War II, a ‘Nouvelle Cité’ was begun in Quartier Dendale (now Commune Kasavubu) for occupation by the African population. The settlements of

Kalina and Leo developed in the 1950s as the city spread to the east growing beyond the Kimbanseke and Masina in the 1960s. After independence, the city continued to grow to the south and southwest (Figure 7) [37, 93, 94]. Kinshasa has grown from a population of 10,000 in 1910 to a megacity with an estimated population of 11.3 million inhabitants in 2018. Kinshasa is the third largest city in Africa after Lagos and Cairo.

Figure 7. Change in spatial extent of Kinshasa between 1969 (129 km²) and 2013 (619km²).

Total surface area of the extents was calculated using the geometry tool in ArcGIS 10 as described in the methods and validated using supplementary information [94].

Historical malaria trends in Kinshasa

Records of the presence of malaria in Kinshasa date back to between 1899 and 1900 [95]. Historical malaria case data in Kinshasa is fragmented, especially for the African population. No comprehensive records on malaria cases specific to Kinshasa were found before 1933 for the European population and 1937 for the African population. An average of 276 cases per year was reported among the 4,500 Europeans living in Kinshasa between 1933 and 1937; representing an average of 37 cases per 1,000 population-at-risk annually. A total of 105,608 malaria cases were documented in Kinshasa in 1938 and 1939 among a population of 84,000 (both African and European) representing an average case incidence of 480 per 1,000 population (Figure 8) [96]. No malaria case data were identified for the period 1940–1948, though it was reported that malaria accounted for 74.4% clinical observations in 1940 increasing to 96.2% by 1945 [97]. A reduction in malaria cases was observed

between 1949 and 1951 with case incidence decreasing from 25 cases per 1000 population to 14 cases per 1000 population. However, the number of cases reported in 1952 tripled to 107,000 from 32,000 in 1951 among a population of approximately 220,000. Case-incidence remained high between 1953 and 1958 with a maximum of just over 1000 cases per 1,000 population reported in 1953.

Figure 8. Annual malaria incidence and population growth in Kinshasa, 1937–1958. Black bars represent malaria cases per 1,000 population for each year. The red line shows total population growth trend in the same period.

Malaria case data assembled from annual colonial medical reports in Belgian Congo published 1938–1958. No case data found before 1938. Case data converted to annual incidence, denominator derived from population estimates in the same period [96]. Inter-censal growth rates between census years computed to estimate populations for non-census years.

The average $PfPR_{2-10}$ reported in 61 surveys conducted in Kinshasa between 1900 and 1959 was 69% with over three-quarters of these studies reporting a parasite rate above 40%. Before the 1960s, most of the Kinshasa was holoendemic with average parasite rates of 75% in children (Figure 9). Although there were only six parasite prevalence studies reported between 1960 and 1979, the average $PfPR_{2-10}$ declined considerably to 17%, ranging between 1% and 47%. The mean $PfPR_{2-10}$ rose between 1980 and 2005 to 39%. More than half of the surveys conducted in this period

reported a mean parasite rate higher than 40%. Malaria prevalence slightly declined between 2006 and 2012 with the mean parasite rate at 21%; only eight of the 134 surveys conducted in this period reported a parasite rate above 40% (Figure 9).

Figure 9. Age standardised *P. falciparum* malaria parasite rates ($PfPR_{2-10}$) in Kinshasa 1900–2012.

Box plot showing median (central lines), 25%, 75% quartile ranges around the median (box width) and upper and lower limits (T). Number of individuals examined by time period: 1900–1959 (11,092); 1960–1979 (1,995); 1980–2005 (39,777) and 2006–2012 (8,401).

Malaria control and prevention in Kinshasa

The first laboratory for public health was established by Henri De Marbaix in 1894, which in 1899 was transferred to the Belgian Society of Colonial Studies, creating the Léopoldville laboratory [98, 99]. Following the establishment of Congo Free State in 1908, colonial authorities quickly established the Colonial Medical Service [99, 100], and in 1922 a separate Colonial Hygiene Service was instituted. Records of malaria control and prevention in Kinshasa date to the early 1920s and show that chemoprophylaxis, environmental measures, vector control and segregation were all employed before World War II.

From quite early on, quinine prophylaxis was used informally by Europeans and among the ‘natives’ [96], and by 1922 African children from selected schools in Kinshasa were receiving preventative

quinine, administered twice-a-week [95]. Environmental modification conducted by the Central government in the late 1930s included major drainage works in Kinshasa from 1937 [97]. European and government houses were fitted with mosquito screens and mosquito net use was reported widely among the European population [96]. In 1931, the sanitary department recommended a minimum separation distance of 800 meters, based on the flight range of the mosquito, between the European and African settlements. Separation required successive relocation of Africans away from the European city with regulations requiring Africans to leave the city at night unless they were an employee (i.e. house help) or had a pass.

During World War II, health services were unavailable, sanitary conditions became worse and malaria control was suspended [97]. Post-war, vector control campaigns were intensified, including IRS with DDT in the late 1940s and a mosquito eradication campaign in 1953. Insecticide spraying from helicopters caused a 90% decrease in mosquito populations at 1000 breeding sites [101]. However, there was rapid reinvasion from untreated zones and the campaign was abandoned in 1954 and replaced with 'reduction campaigns' of monthly household spraying [101].

In 1976, the *Program de Lutte Antipaludique* was launched by an agreement between the United States Agency for International Development (USAID) and the Government with an aim to implement and evaluate malaria vector control measures in Kinshasa. The primary anopheline mosquito control measure was IRS with DDT [102]. Originally based in Ndjili, Masina, Kimbanseke, and Limete zones Kinshasa, the programme was extended to other zones of Kinshasa beginning in late 1981. During the late 1980s, with the escalation of civil conflict triggered by the Rwandan genocide and the interruption of the bilateral cooperation, USAID left Kinshasa and malaria activities stopped [102]. This coincided with the emergence and spread of chloroquine and pyrimethamine resistance [102-105]. Between 2000 and 2015 there were no special programs aimed at urban

malaria control within the Kinshasa city limits. However, distribution of ITNs and later LLINs was supported by several internationally funded programmes [106, 107], and a sentinel site was established in Kinshasa for monitoring insecticide resistance [108].

Discussion

The reliability and completeness of the official malaria case data is likely to be poor. Nevertheless, data were reported by colonial medical authorities most years, though more comprehensively for European versus African populations. To circumvent biases of case reporting, parasite prevalence was used as this was often recorded in all populations irrespective of race. Close to 550 parasite prevalence surveys were identified spanning from 1900 to 2012 across the three cities.

All three cities discussed in this paper were established in areas with intense malaria transmission. Between 1900 and 1960, the reported mean $PfPR_{2-10}$ was 57% in Lagos, 50% in Dar es Salaam and 69% in Kinshasa. This demonstrates the receptive potential for malaria in these localities and that malaria was already a large public health threat as these cities evolved into urban centres between the two World Wars.

The post-independence period marked a significant reduction in malaria prevalence rates in Dar es Salaam and Kinshasa with a mean $PfPR_{2-10}$ of 17% recorded between 1960 and 1979 in both cities, though over this period the $PfPR_{2-10}$ remained high in Lagos at 51%. Following independence and post-GMEP in Africa, there was a shift in focus away from vector control to treating presumed malaria fevers. It is therefore perhaps not surprising that there were far fewer parasite prevalence surveys during the 1960s and 1970s. Despite the paucity of data, malaria prevalence continued or began to decline during this period in Dar es Salaam and Kinshasa. These decades were characterised by unprecedented urban expansion as surrounding wetlands were reclaimed and forested areas cleared to make room for residential and industrial buildings, reducing potential

mosquito breeding areas. At the same time, the population in the three cities increased enormously with population densities almost tripling from 1960 to 1980. Malaria prevalence rates remained high, possibly maintained by mass migration from highly endemic rural areas. With millions of residents, the number of people at risk of malaria infection was much higher compared to the colonial era.

There was a resurgence of malaria in Kinshasa and Dar es Salaam between 1980 and 2005, with mean parasite rates increasing to 39% in and 25%, respectively. Although only four community surveys were found in records searched in Lagos during this period, mean parasite rate was also high at 24%, but had declined relative to 1960–1979 (51%). Precipitated by the decline in chloroquine efficacy, increasing malaria mortality was recognised as a public health disaster [109, 110]. It was also a period of political change across Africa, and in Kinshasa a period of major civil strife.

Population growth rates remained high, a growing proportion of the population engaged in informal employment and living in unplanned settlements which contributed to the increasing transmission rates as urban mosquito breeding sites proliferated.

In the period between 2006 and 2012, malaria was reported within all three urban areas with parasite prevalence ranging between 7–21%. During this period, there was mass deployment of ITNs and LLINs, and the introduction of RDTs and ACTs. These interventions are likely responsible for the reduced malaria prevalence and mortality over this period versus historical data.

The efforts to prevent and control malaria enacted across the three cities are varied and extensive (Table 1). However, it is impossible to make any direct conclusion as to the impact of any of the interventions on malaria prevalence for several reasons. Firstly, there are the limitations in the data which may vary in their consistency, reliability and methods of collection, so small changes year on

year most likely represent ‘noise’ in the surveillance system. Secondly, operational evaluation of interventions was not often systematically conducted and there are no control data against which to make any judgement as to the success of a particular intervention. It would, therefore, be misleading to retrospectively attribute any changes in malaria prevalence to an intervention based only on the temporal relationship. Even when the impact of interventions was evaluated, such as UMCP in Dar es Salaam, it was difficult for researchers to tease out the complex competing factors that might influence parasite prevalence in the dynamic and heterogeneous urban setting. However, it appears clear that when interventions are scaled back, stopped or defeated by parasite or vector resistance, malaria prevalence increases.

Table 1. Historical approaches for malaria control and prevention in the three urban case studies.

Environmental modification	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Improving drainage Draining swamps Dredging to increase water flow Making embankments Land reclamation Forest clearance Planting coconut trees to drain the soil Tidal flooding control Improved sanitation
Social/ preventive	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> House/window screening Improved housing Segregation, buffer zones and relocation Bed nets (no insecticide) Mosquito brigades and sanitary policemen House inspections to discover and remove breeding sites
Vector control	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Larviciding with fuel oil, chemicals and microbial agents Aerial spraying of insecticides Indoor residual spraying with insecticides Insecticide-treated bed nets Larvivorous fish Risk mapping Entomological surveillance of breeding sites Monitoring of insecticide resistance
Antimalarial drugs	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> Prophylaxis (quinine, chloroquine) Intermittent prevention in children Treatment at home/ informal sector to increase access Mass screen and treat

Conclusions

The pioneers of malaria control developed new approaches with the technologies that were available. They instituted integrated vector control, relying heavily on deploying insecticides and environmental modification, as well as promoting quinine and later chloroquine prophylaxis. However, they found that reducing vector populations did not always reduce malaria transmission and the emergence and spread of insecticide and chloroquine resistance ultimately led to a disastrous malaria resurgence. Thus, it is not enough to reduce vector populations, rather attention must be paid to operational effectiveness in reducing the human malaria burden and strategies that have the potential to interrupt transmission.

The heterogeneity of breeding sites and a diversity of vector species with different bionomics means that any single approach will almost certainly fail. Today, new mapping and surveillance technologies enable resources and interventions to be focused on the most important vector populations and key transmission reservoirs at a very high level of granularity in urban settings [6, 44, 111]. Similarly, advances in diagnosis, surveillance and information systems also allow cases to be discovered and mapped very accurately. However, this increased information is useful only if it triggers an effective response. At present there is a gap between being able to describe very carefully the vector and disease characteristics of the urban environment, and being able to design a bespoke response for each specific situation that suppresses vector populations, treats infection, and enhances and sustains malaria protection. It is also key that the impact of a response can be evaluated. However, evaluation methods must consider the rapidly changing and complex urban environment and potential confounders.

Political, social and human factors are critical but often overlooked areas for research and policy development in malaria control. Without improvements in housing, sanitation, drainage and

infrastructure, vector habitats will proliferate and transmission will be perpetually maintained. In urban areas, there is enormous scope to incorporate strategies into planning, design and building that limit vector breeding sites. For example, in 2015 about half of the urban population of sub-Saharan Africa, an estimated 53 million people, were living in unimproved housing, without adequate access to water, sanitation or durable shelter [112]. Though malaria contributes to poverty, so poverty provides the conditions in which malaria can be sustained. Thus, social policy should consider the potential 'malaria dividend' that can result from improving people's living conditions, healthcare access, economic opportunities and education.

Successive administrators of urban areas have discovered that implementation of top-down policies will inevitably exclude the disenfranchised and peripheral communities that mushroom around rapidly growing urban centres. Involvement and support from these communities must be engaged and mobilised to target malaria within the most vulnerable populations.

It is clear that re-learning the lessons of the past by depending on a limited choice of insecticides broadly applied, and a single class of antimalarial drug sub-optimally deployed will be very costly. Thus, we must fully acknowledge the failures and successes of all past approaches and apply all our current knowledge, technology and tools in concert to address the increasingly complex setting for the control of urban malaria across sub-Saharan Africa. It is now time to design, implement and evaluate efficient integrated vector control models for the 21st century to support malaria control and elimination specifically targeted at the urban environment. As in the past, whatever technologies and strategies are employed, their success will ultimately depend on community engagement, economic sustainability and political support.

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